

Nurturing Microbiome Research

Diversifying Domains for Sustainable Public Health Changes

Microbiome research stands at the intersection of science, ethics, and society, resonating with our evolving understanding of life. Emphasising symbiosis, connectedness, and mutual dependence, this field holds promise for revolutionizing healthcare and lifestyle choices. This factsheet highlights the ethical and philosophical dimensions of microbiome research to ensure its responsible and inclusive advancement.

WHAT DO WE KNOW?

- Microbiome research aligns with contemporary views of life, emphasising symbiotic relationships and interconnectedness.
- A significant portion of citizens demonstrate a willingness to monitor their microbiome and adapt their lifestyle to enhance microbiome health. Understanding the human microbiome, e.g. microbiome health, not only requires insight into microbiological composition and physiological function but also in behaviour, health experience, lifestyle, values, self-image and worldview.
- Collaboration across disciplines, including life sciences, social sciences, and the humanities, enriches microbiome research by integrating diverse perspectives and methodologies.

Figure 1: Perception of the human microbiome – An online survey among representative samples from France, Germany, South Korea and Taiwan; N=2858

WHERE ARE WE GOING?

Engaging citizens in microbiome research fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment over personal health, bringing a new public health dimension to address e.g. through the inclusion of participatory citizen science, projects in microbiome research.

Collaborative efforts between different fields expand the scope of microbiome research, leading to innovative solutions and holistic understandings of human health.

Ethical considerations guide the responsible conduct of research, ensuring that societal values and concerns are addressed.

CONCLUSION

Microbiome research holds ethical and philosophical dimensions, emphasising the importance of responsible conduct and inclusive participation. By integrating diverse perspectives and fostering collaboration, microbiome research will advance in a manner that promotes societal well-being as well as scientific excellence.

Ready to make microbiome research more inclusive and involve public knowledge in the understanding of microbiome health?

Join our Stakeholder Advisory Board to provide strategic advice from an external point of view or engage with the [European Microbiome Centres Consortium](#) to foster interdisciplinary collaboration.

For further information, please visit our website humanmicrobiomeaction.eu. Follow the @SciFoodHealth [Twitter/X](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts or connect through the [Sustainable Food Systems Network Microbiome Subgroup](#).

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